

**THE SIGNIFICANCE AND SIGNIFICANCE OF INNOVATIVE
TECHNOLOGY IN THE DEVELOPMENT OF THE ELITE WHEELING
FARM**

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Brewed state beer is brewed using an agricultural barrel-sized farm brewing unit. For example, in Japan, small-sized carpentry is the majority, while large-sized carpentry is dominant in Amepika Joint Stock Company. At the moment, the products produced by the company are being marketed not only in the local market, but also around the world with the added value system. "OECD-FAO agricultural perspective organization in 2019-2028 estimates that the demand for agricultural products will increase by 15% in the next ten years ¹. " "In order to satisfy the increasing need for food products, the priority of using new technology in agriculture, increasing the yield, rather than expanding the farm is recognized ². "

Therefore, after the global economic crisis, especially the negative impact of the COVID-19 crisis on the results of 2020, global production is expected to grow by 4% in 2021, but this multiplier is much lower than before the pandemic ³. This, in turn, requires the use of the innovative experience of an economically developed country to strengthen the flexibility policy of the economy and prevent negative changes.

According to researches, the effectiveness of innovation and the degree of involvement of the producer in the innovative Japan in many ways play an important role in the success of entering the world agricultural market and the competitiveness of the agricultural producer, as well as in providing the population with safe food.

Improving the competitiveness and efficiency of agricultural products based on the modernization of agriculture in our country and the development, implementation and use of innovations in this field, the promotion of innovative activities dolzabp is becoming an issue. In this regard, the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan decided to "fundamentally improve the mechanism of innovation activity by the state, more efficiently integrate innovation into the economy and the sector ⁴, modernize and

¹OECD/FAO (2019), OECD-FAO Agricultural Outlook 2019-2028, OECD Publishing, Paris/Food and Agriculture Organization of the United Nations, Rome. https://doi.org/10.1787/agr_outlook-2019-en.

²Megatrends in the agri-food sector: global overview and possible policy response from an EU perspective. Policy Department for Structural and Cohesion Policies Directorate-General for Internal Policies PE 629.205 – September 2019. <https://www.europarl.europa.eu/>

³Global and Regional Outlooks. <https://www.worldbank.org/en/publication/global-economic-prospects>

⁴Decision PQ-3698 dated May 7, 2018 of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On additional measures to improve the mechanisms for introducing innovations into economic sectors and sectors". <https://lex.uz/docs/3723561>

diversify production, increase its volume, and expand the range of competitive products on the domestic and foreign markets." ⁵related tasks are defined. Therefore, the effective solution of the tasks set before agriculture requires increasing the productivity of agricultural products based on the stimulation of innovative activities in our country.

An innovative product appears when the results of scientific research in agriculture are applied to development and the results of this product meet the needs of the market. Its inventive part fulfills a well-defined task in general Japan: for example, it makes innovations in the field of science, in development - it is used, and the finished product gets its own medicine.

It is worth noting that in agriculture, the innovative part of the innovative structure, which is usually created based on the demand for a new idea and development, organizes its activities in accordance with the consumer's demand. Therefore, there is a very important step of innovative Japanese development in agriculture (figure 1).

Figure 1. The stage of ⁶Japanese innovation in the implementation of a new idea in the field of agriculture .

⁵Decree No. PF-5544 of September 21, 2018 of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On approval of the innovative development strategy of the Republic of Uzbekistan in 2019-2021". <https://lex.uz/docs/3913188>

⁶Source. Author development based on research results

In order to fully realize the innovative Japanese stage in the field of agriculture, to transfer the product of intellectual work from one innovative stage to the next, first of all, to the level of knowledge, and secondly, to overcome the problem of development and implementation of new technology, what kind of competition should be faced.

There are three logical forms of innovative behavior: internal (within the company), external (in relation to the organization) and extended form. In this case, a simple intra-organizational innovation process involves the implementation of innovation within the organization and the use of resources, but in this case, innovation does not directly take the form of reward.

The external organization operates as a trading facility with innovative Japanese innovations. Expanded innovation industry involves creating a new innovative idea, breaking the monopoly of the existing producer, which is able to improve the consumer characteristics, quality and competitiveness of the competitive product. At least two economic entities, the developer (closer) and the consumer (user) of the innovation, are active in the extended innovation industry.

If we take into account the use of biological agents for the implementation of innovation activities in agriculture, especially in breeding, and the specific features of the internal and external structure of the agricultural production system, it is necessary to mention the clearly oriented classification of innovations in the agrop sector of the economy.

While the modern activity in the field of agriculture coincides with the innovative development of the industry - the organization and promotion of scientific research in this direction is a dependent form of development, the improvement of product quality and labor productivity, the implementation of scientific results, the development of production with modern technological and technical means, in the field A suite of software to support the modern business environment.

In relation to production, innovation in agriculture should be understood as the creation of new or improved agricultural machinery, tools, technology, improvement of technology, organization of production using scientific research and advanced technology. Based on the opinion mentioned above, in our opinion, increasing the competitiveness of agricultural products based on the promotion of innovative activities The formation of an economic mechanism related to bran should be carried out in the direction of bip kapatap.

The discovery of the economic mechanism of the innovative development of the farming sector includes the specific form and method of organizing and promoting innovative activity, as well as the main tasks that need to be solved. The entire chain of innovation application in agriculture includes promoting the innovative activity of the economic

entity, developing the potential of the business entity related to the use of innovation (innovative, technological, educational, scientific, economic), increasing the investment attractiveness of the sector, and developing the infrastructure and agricultural production base.

In our opinion, it is innovative in breeding. As an active means of organizing and promoting activities, it is important to have an active participation of state capital in the principle of public-private partnership. This makes it possible for the state to use the mechanism that encourages the cooperation of private business in the development of innovative Japanese beer. It is necessary to create a competitive environment in the field, along with the efficient distribution of the labor force, the reduction of the problem for the training.

The experience shows that the innovative development in the agropap sector is to give preference to the research conducted on the basis of the technical topics in the field of agropap business in the national initiative of the research activity of the industrial scientific research institute, to connect the business, university and scientific map with the innovative small enterprise of the state scientific activity. It is necessary to carry out a thorough promotion.

The formation of a strategic base related to the promotion of innovative breeding of horticulture is an important part of the economic mechanism of innovative breeding of the agropap industry. Because the economic mechanism can be effectively implemented only if there is a functioning legal basis.

As an important part of the economic mechanism of the innovative development of breeding, it is recommended to develop the system of material and technical support, which is closed to the innovative development of the industry. In this:

- to ensure the guarantee of the right to use the forest for the agricultural economy during the legally defined period (from 30 to 50 years);
- to equip the agricultural farm with agricultural machinery, mineral fertilizers, and oil products;
- the issue of promoting the use of modern technology, cost-effective technical means should find its own solution.

In our opinion, in the formation of innovative activity in agriculture, on the basis of the subject of advanced development, agrotechnopapklap, technopolispap (technological map), scientific and development mapkazlap activities require special attention to the implementation of innovative ideas. In this context, the main task of the technogroup is to grow the growth of agricultural crops, develop energy-saving technologies, develop new high-quality product groups, improve environmental safety and competitiveness of crops, make scientific and technological achievements in agricultural processing and

food industry (biology and biotechnology). In order to find out the results, it is necessary to establish a consultation system in the region.

Of course, the formation of a technopolis in agriculture serves to carry out scientific research, develop a new design for product packaging, create the latest technology and equipment, create and re-create a new agricultural product variety, qualified scientific staff for science and education.

In order to implement the organizational-economic mechanism of innovation activity and development in agriculture, it is necessary to study the social-economic relationship that dictates the adaptation of the scientific, innovative and economic activities of the organization and the company to the ever-changing environment. The economic mechanism of managing and stimulating innovation development includes financial, credit, investment, planning, supply policy, and stimulation of the development of the material and technical base of innovation. Of course, there is also a factor that has a negative impact on the development of innovative activities in agriculture, as in other fields. Including:

- non-emergency of weather and natural disasters (drought, flood, global climate change);
- decrease in the professional level of economic workers and, in general, agrobusiness;
- lack of investment in the development and implementation of innovative projects in the development of sorghum farming;
- the low level of innovation activity of the agricultural sector and the underdevelopment of the innovation infrastructure.

In order to ensure success in the transition of the farming industry to the path of innovative development, there are important tasks in the innovative development of the agro-industrial complex, including:

- development and implementation of efficient waste-saving technologies based on localization, increasing the competitiveness and export potential of innovative developments in the agricultural sector;
- development of a set of "advanced technologies" within the framework of the localization initiative, which determines the possibility of forming a new market for high-tech products, based on the improvement of the existing technology, for the production of high-quality grain and meat, cotton wool and other new agricultural products for the local product sector;
- to carry out technical and technological modernization of agricultural infrastructure and infrastructure on the basis of long-term contracts and leasing.

of state support for increasing the competitiveness and export potential of the high-tech innovation sector in agriculture is the state initiative, which provides financing for the most promising projects.

To sum up, the organizational and economic nature of the innovative Japanese approach in brewing is related to the goal and task of brewing, and it is a constant organizational, economic, technical and technological update that is focused on improving the agricultural production in the context of science, technology, and world experience. In this case, the main goal of the innovative development of the industry is to form an innovative base of agriculture.

REVIEW OF USED LITERATURE

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